

THE ROLE OF CULTURAL-PUBLIC EVENTS IN SOCIAL LIFE

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of cultural and public events in social life, organizational features, and some socio-psychological problems.

Key words: culture, art, cultural-public events, social life, aesthetic factor, celebration, organization, audience.

The functional characteristics of cultural and mass events are that they affect the life of people and society through a complex of tools, such as music, dance, theater, spectacle, technical, performance, public movement, live speech, figurative symbols, art artifacts, visual arts. They have the opportunity to synthesize all types of art and creativity and create a unified reality - a public viewing environment. Forming the necessary imaginations, interests and views in a person by creating a complex and synthesized artistic-aesthetic environment is the social essence of cultural-public events.

Social life, according to its substantial basis, is colorful, contradictory, multifactorial. According to philosophers, today's social life is very different from that of previous historical stages. In it, the desire of people and social values to popularize is strong [1, S.388-389]. Incorporation of these aspects is a characteristic of cultural and public events. Popularization is not the destruction of uniqueness, individual-spiritual aspects, phylogenetic development in a person, turning a person into an "abstract group" [1, S.388]. Popularization is an attribute of social life, when a person lives together with society, he achieves his dreams and life goals. Cultural and public events also contribute to this.

In cultural studies and art studies, there is almost no definition of cultural-public events recognized by the scientific community. Because both a lecture attended by 20-30 people and a show organized on a large square can be called a cultural-public event or a public holiday [2; 3; 4].

On the one hand, it is possible to understand the reason for such an approach, where the lack of scientific and epistemological studies related to the field is noticeable. On the other hand, empirical experiments cannot continue in a chaotic, eclectic way, because the ideological, educational and sociological influence of cultural-mass events is extremely strong. So, at this point, we should say that cultural and public events have the power to bring people together, to form common ideas, beliefs, life goals and ideals in them. encourages approach.

There are many factors influencing the development of society, including democracy, globalization, external integration, economic, political and family relations, migration processes, market democracy, management system, social opinion, public sentiment. Cultural and public events can be dedicated to each of them or receive orders from each of them. For example, the creation of material and spiritual wealth of private property owners in the market democracy can be organized by meeting parties, exhibitions, and educational events based on the example of good, humanitarian and leadership work of an owner. A creative school for talented children built by the big businessman A.Usmonov can be a source for cultural and public events. Or it is appropriate to organize a theatrical performance, an educational and promotional night about the strategy of development.

Today, paradigmatic changes are taking place in the life of our society. Constitutional reforms can give any topic to cultural-public events. So, for cultural and public events, you can find as many sources as you want from every field, even from every day. It is about the creative activity of cultural workers and managers who organize events. Cultural and public events have a great educational impact on the formation of social opinion. This is clearly confirmed by the answers of our respondents. During Navroz celebrations, viewers are asked "What aspects of Navroz holiday do you like the most?" to our question, 53% of our respondents said "Closeness to nature", 43% "Festive mood", 41% "Reference to our history", 35% "Walking in the open air, attending a show", 24% "It evokes harmony, unity", 22% "Relaxation, recreation" release", 14% said "It is possible to meet friends, get to know each other", 11% said "Family vacation", 7% "Making the neighborhood more compact", 6% "Arousing a reaction to folk traditions". "Closeness to nature" is the leading answer. This idea is deeply rooted in the minds of our people. Doctor of Philosophy, Professor V. Alimasov, in the philosophical and sociological research conducted in the second half of the 90s, found out that the respondents give a leading place to recreation in the open air, by the water [5, 43-45 p.]. These answers indicate that it is a tradition in our nation to seek outdoor recreation.

Cultural and public events create a festive mood. The social opinion of young people is formed under the influence of this aesthetic and psychological factor. According to young people, the festive mood encourages fun, creative pursuits and social activity. The creation of cultural assets, the formation of moral values and vital, aesthetic ideals also depends on the mood of a person. Although psychological mood is a momentary feeling, it has the power to give purpose and direction to human life. Especially the festive mood forms corporate, general thoughts among young people, so it is observed that people who are strangers to each other quickly become friendly and united during the holidays. This socio-psychological factor in cultural-public events is a unique opportunity for a manager and director.

Today, the spheres of social life are becoming more and more differentiated, each type of activity is characterized by intensive development. This requires a person to have deep knowledge and research on his work. The influence of moral and spiritual load increases and negatively affects a person's mind and mood. That is why scientists note that hypodynamia, nervousness, ischemia, and physical weakness are increasing. Hypodynamia, which has been called the "disease of the century", requires high mobility and activity from a person, especially a young organism. Cultural and public events, for example, sports games and performances, competitions educate mobility and agility in a person, and form a healthy lifestyle. 35 percent of our respondents associate walking in the open air with such qualities. Walking in the open air, walking, climbing mountains and hills, crossing streams and ditches, picking flowers or herbs have a positive effect on the human body and psyche, and a city dweller living in a limited environment can find them in a new way. perceives a world, a world of pleasure, as a source of creativity and inspiration. Nature is colorful, it pleases a person's eyes with its diversity and expands their thoughts. "One thinks narrowly in a narrow place" [F. Dostoevsky], and wide nature makes thoughts boundless. So, the place of cultural and public events in social life is when it brings a person closer to nature, when it brings nature and man closer to each other.

Cultural and public events make a person familiar with the values respected by the society, bring the norms, customs and procedures that stabilize the social existence into his mind and lifestyle. The above response "Refers to our history" [41 percent] confirms that events help to build historical awareness. Experts say that the formation of social consciousness occurs through the "I" of the individual. The national mentality and historical-cultural assets, which are the product of historical processes, play an important role in it [6, 33, 41 p.].

A person who has mastered these artifacts or assimilated them into his mind and lifestyle will not remain indifferent to the events. Our respondents say that celebrating Nowruz introduces them to the life, rituals and holidays of our ancestors, encourages them to study historical monuments, and shapes their spiritual world and national consciousness. This shows that cultural and public events have a positive effect on people's consciousness and lifestyle. Historical consciousness, interest in historical and cultural wealth does not arise in a person by itself, it requires certain socio-pedagogical mechanisms, methods and tools.

24 percent of our respondents say that the celebration of Nowruz awakens the idea of harmony, union and living together in people's minds. Yes, one of the tasks envisaged in cultural and public events is to encourage people to live together. In general, cultural and public events are not just a means of spending time and entertainment, but they are focused on fulfilling a certain ideological, educational and educational task. The social essence in them is to raise the national culture by performing this task in a cultural way, using cultural means [7, P.14-15.]. Therefore, the goal of raising the national culture requires massification of events, massification ensures that the cultural artefact takes place in the people's consciousness and lifestyle.

Researcher A.I. Mazaev said that artistic-aesthetic tools, expressions and methods used in cultural and public events ensure that holidays take place in social life, consciousness and imagination. A person goes to a holiday to enjoy these artistic and aesthetic methods, and that's the reason for the good mood [8, S. 127-128.] During the holiday, the process leading up to the event, that is, the pre-holiday stage, is very important. In this regard, it is very important to arouse the festive mood in the population, to involve them in the organization of the event, and to activate them. A.I. Mazaev also emphasizes this socio-psychological factor. Because relying on the initiative and participation of the population publicizes the idea and purpose of the holiday, enlivens the event. According to experts who have studied the psychology of art, human attention consists of undirected, directed and post-directed stages. A holiday mood is a special focus of attention because it focuses thoughts, ideas, and goals on the holiday. People focus on the holiday and expect something from it. This "something" can be a new impression, a new acquaintance or friend, gaining a sense of belonging, getting rid of a psychophysiological load, clearing the mind, or even just spending time.

"The inner psychological space" [K. Stanislavsky] encourages a person to enrich himself with new impressions, as a result, attention is focused on these new impressions, in our example, a holiday. The festive mood makes the focus clearly targeted or hypothetical [9. S. 48.]. Hypothetical attention is a way of giving direction to dreams, imagination and hopes. The spectator directs his pre-holiday hypothetical attention to something (making a new friend, getting new information, getting rid of psychophysiological burden, etc.) and expects something unusual, something new from the event. If his demand is not met, he will not be satisfied with the holiday event. Therefore, there is a dialectical connection between the audience's hypothetical attention or goal and his satisfaction with the cultural-public event, his joy and happiness. If the balance of the dialectical relationship between them,

If the "aesthetic dialogue" mentioned by K. Stanislavsky is broken, the holiday will remain an ordinary reality. A holiday, according to its social essence, is not a regular event that repeats every day, it is an unusual event that does not repeat every day and requires special hypothetical attention. The unique phenomenon, originality and novelty of cultural and public events arouses artistic and aesthetic interest in a person. The transformation of cultural and mass events into a unique spectacle that matches the audience's hypothetical attention requires the experience of effectively using all the possibilities and tools of culture and art.

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